

Conference Abstract

Towards a genome variation atlas of the weatherfish (*Misgurnus fossilis*) in the Low Countries

Hendrik-Jan Megens[‡], Io Deflem[§], Maarten Bruns[|], Arjan P Palstra[‡], Reindert Nijland[¶], Stan Coppis[¶], Mick Vos[|], Jelger Herder[|], Jeroen Van Wichelen[#], Johan Auwerx[□], Joachim Mergeay[§]

[‡] Wageningen University and Research, Animal Breeding & Genomics, Wageningen, Netherlands

[§] INBO Research Institute for Nature and Forest, Geraardsbergen, Belgium

[|] RAVON Reptielen Amfibieën Vissen Onderzoek Nederland, Nijmegen, Netherlands

[¶] Wageningen University and Research, Marine Animal Ecology, Wageningen, Netherlands

[#] INBO Research Institute for Nature and Forest, Brussels, Belgium

[□] INBO Research Institute for Nature and Forest, Linkebeek, Belgium

Corresponding author: Hendrik-Jan Megens (hendrik-jan.megens@wur.nl)

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Abstract

The weatherfish (*Misgurnus fossilis*) was once widespread across the floodplains of rivers in Northwestern Europe. Today, it serves as an important indicator species for marshy wetlands. Most remaining populations are now considered relics, and many continue to decline, which may result in loss of genetic diversity, and even inbreeding depression, increasing the risks of local extinction. To support effective management and restoration of these relic populations, a better understanding of their genetic diversity, biogeographic structure, and demographic history is needed. Here we present an initiative to characterize the genome diversity of the weatherfish across Belgium and The Netherlands. Since genome resources for the species are currently lacking, our initiative includes the development of a genome assembly and functional annotation. In collaboration with governmental stakeholders, we have initiated a pilot project to re-sequence genomes of weatherfish in three biogeographically distinct areas, each with specific population management objectives. By applying a genome re-sequencing strategy, these and future efforts can be integrated in a regional genome variation atlas

for the weatherfish. Such a resource is particularly valuable for interpreting results from marginalized populations where obtaining more than just a few fish to sample has become a serious challenge. Ultimately a regional genome variation atlas will not only inform local conservation strategies, but can also contribute to a European genome variation atlas for the weatherfish.

Presenting author

Hendrik-Jan Megens

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Conflicts of interest

The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.